

**INNOVATIONS AND POPULATION WELL-BEING:
RELATIONSHIP, TREND, PERSPECTIVES**

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Abstract: Common methodologies of well-being and innovation activity assessment are described and a new way of well-being and innovation activity measurement is considered. Subsequent comparative analysis of world countries well-being and innovation activity indicators let to detect its relation and make conclusions on the topic.

Keywords: innovations, innovation activity, well-being, standard of living

Introduction The consequences of the global crisis have once again demonstrated the significant dependence of our country's economy on energy prices and revealed the problems of the "raw material" path of development. It became clear that the condition for the normal economic functioning of Russia in the long term is to overcome the technological gap with the most developed countries of the world. The changes that have taken place all over the world demonstrate the need to switch to a new model of economic development based on new technologies and innovative solutions. Therefore, it is not surprising that the concepts of "innovation" and "innovative economy" are now very often heard-both in the statements of politicians of all countries, in the press, and in various economic studies. In relation to developed countries, a special term "innovative economy" is put forward and used. This is "a type of economy based on the flow of innovations, on constant technological improvement, on the production and export of high-tech products with very high added value and the technologies themselves" [17]. High technologies and new innovative solutions have a significant impact on many aspects of public life,

changing people's living conditions for the better. However, the relationship between innovation and the standard of living is not one-sided, since a high standard of living is one of the most important conditions for the interest of the state and society in innovation. Only in those societies where all the basic human needs have already been met, it is possible to realize the importance of innovations. The emergence of new technologies requires a developed infrastructure, affordable education and a high level of human capital development. The fact that spending on education and science is necessary for the development of the country is often mentioned, but much less often the idea that a high level of development of economic and social institutions is necessary for the development and implementation of innovations. If we talk about those countries that are considered to live in an innovative economy, then the transition to a new way of life took place against the background of progressive and highly mechanized production, with a developed infrastructure and in conditions of high domestic demand. Thus, a kind of spiral is created – the development of society stimulates innovative technologies, and those in their lives raise the quality of life to an even higher level. It is the relationship between innovation and the standard of living of the population that will be investigated in our work. 2. The terminological apparatus and the main hypotheses of the study

Improving the standard of living of the population is the main goal of any progressive society. In many countries, the main strategy is to increase the cost of human development. Indicators of the quality of life and human development become a criterion for decision-making in the field of economic and social policy. At the same time, Russia is increasingly lagging behind developed countries in these indicators. To study the standard of living in Russia and conduct international comparisons, we will define the terminological base of the study. It should be noted that the concept of welfare will be used under the standard of living in work. Well-

being is an integral set, a stable system of socio-economic living conditions that have developed in a given society and the satisfaction of the needs of an individual or a social group. The category of "welfare" is manifested in the scale of the needs of an individual or a social group and in the volumes, forms, methods and conditions of their satisfaction [8].

There are two methodological approaches to measuring the achieved level of well-being: The first approach, which can be defined as subjective, proceeds from the assessment of well-being as the degree of subjective satisfaction of people with their lives. In this case, a person himself evaluates how good or bad his life is according to certain criteria, so an idea of the well-being of each individual can be obtained only from the results of sociological research. As a result, the assessment of well-being is based on the opinion of the population expressed on certain aspects of life [8]. When using the second approach, well-being is assessed not by subjective satisfaction with the person himself, but by a number of objective indicators using a survey of experts. This approach involves the construction of a system of indicators or socio-economic indicators that most fully reflects the multidimensional well-being of the population, and the definition of norms or social standards with which the actual conditions for the formation of the well-being of the population are compared. Many international and regional intergovernmental organizations are engaged in the development of systems of indicators that characterize the well-being of the population. It should be noted that at present there is no clear methodology for calculating welfare. Quite a lot of different systems of indicators of the standard of living of the population have been developed, which differ in the structure and set of indicators. In the study of the welfare of the population, we will use the following indicators. The Human Development Index (HDI), which has been published annually by the UN in the Human Development Report since 1990 [18]. The HDI is

a standard tool for general comparison of the standard of living of different countries and regions. The HDI is a geometric average of normalized indices reflecting achievements in the following three areas: life expectancy; the level of literacy of the country's population (the average number of years spent on education) and the expected duration of education; GNI per capita at purchasing power parity (PPP) in US dollars. The study also included indicators obtained from the sections "Perception of individual well-being and well-being" and "Civil and public well-being". - Housing affordability (% of satisfied respondents) – - Health care quality (% of satisfied respondents) – - Education system and schools (% of satisfied respondents) – - Air quality (% of satisfied respondents) – - Water quality (% of satisfied respondents) – - Perception of safety (% of satisfied respondents); – Overall life satisfaction (from 0 (the most dissatisfied) to 10-the most satisfied) – - Work (% of satisfied working respondents) – - Personal health (% of the total number of satisfied respondents). To characterize the stratification of society, we took into account indicators that characterize the degree of differentiation of the population by income level, which, in our opinion, has a significant impact on innovation activity. Innovative activity. In the study of innovation activity, we relied on the Methodological Recommendations of the Organization for Economic Development and the Commonwealth (OECD (English spelling OECD), which develops the basic concepts and definitions related to innovation. The Oslo Guidelines are the main OECD working document on innovation research [2]. According to this Guide, " Innovation is the final result of innovative activity, embodied in the form of a new or improved product (product, work, service) introduced on the market, a new or improved technological process, or an organizational or marketing method used in practical activities." It should be noted that the assessment of the level of innovation potential in the world practice is carried out according to various methods, among

which one can distinguish: - The index of scientific and technical potential as a component of an integral indicator for assessing the level of competitiveness of a country [3]; - The system for assessing the country's innovation activity in accordance with the indicators of the European Innovation Scale (EIS) [4] – - The system of indicators for assessing the innovation activity of countries according to the OECD methodology [5]; - The Methodology for assessing knowledge (KAM- the Knowledge Assessment Methodology) [6]; - Global Innovation Index (GII or GII)[7]; - International Innovation Index [9] – - ranking of countries by the level of innovation [10]. In the study and comparison of the innovation activity of countries, we used the World Bank indicators [19]: 1. The number of new enterprises opened annually per able-bodied resident of the country (New businesses registered (number)/Laborforce, total); 2. Investment in R & D, in % of GDP (Research and development expenditure, % of GDP); 3. The share of high-tech exports, as a % of exports of manufactured goods (High – technology exports, % of manufactured exports); 4. The share of income of service enterprises, as a % of GDP, (Services, etc., valueadded, % ofGDP); 5. The share of income of industrial enterprises, as a % of GDP (Manufacturing, value added, % of GDP); 6. The amount of loans granted to private business, as a % of GDP (Domestic credit to private sector, % of GDP) 7. The strength of legal rights (a special indicator, where 0 – extremely weak compliance with legal rights, 10-strong rights) (Strength of legal rights index (0=weakt to 10=strong)); 8. Taxes on income, profit and capital gains, % of total taxes (Taxes on income, profits and capital gains, % of total taxes).

Reference:

1. Gorina E. E. Labor market research: an interdisciplinary approach // Modern Economics: problems, trends, prospects. - 2011-No. 5-p. 1-7.
2. Employment of the population in spontaneous trade and service: economic and sociological research / under the general editorship of S. V. Ryazantsev; Institute of Socio-Political Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences. - M.: Nauka, 2004-216 p.
3. Sankova L. V. problems of formation of an innovative type of employment in the modern economy // Innovative processes in education, science and economy at the threshold of the XXI century : mezhdunar. nauch.–pract. Conf. Part 2 (Orenburg, Jan. 1998). – Orenburg, 1998 – Pp. 95-96.
4. Starovoitova L. I. Employment and its regulation : proc. manual / L. I. Starovoitova, T. F. Zolotareva. - M.: Academy, 2001-190
5. Ismatov, S. A. (2019). Determination of the relationship of the quality of life with the living standard of the population. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 10 (78), 501-505.
6. Ismatov, S. A., & Ortikov, S. M. (2020). The population bandhini tamines, Turmus of Regine oshirildi humiliation Tagirova and using Uzbekistana characteristic. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11 (91), 521-526.